

Emotional States of Blood Donors and Non-blood Donors

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Blood donation constitutes a critical component of health care systems, supporting life-saving treatments and enhancing population health worldwide. The only source of blood is voluntary donations. The constant demand for secure blood supplies, especially for patients with rare blood groups and in times of emergency, emphasizes the significance of blood donation. Recruitment of blood donors is an important issue worldwide. The purpose of the present research is to assess and compare the level of happiness and anxiety of blood donors and non-blood donors. A multigroup design was used in the present study. For this purpose, a sample of 250 male participants was taken and equally divided into five groups. Group-I have the participants who donated blood for the 1 time, group-II comprised of the participants who have donated blood 2 to 3 times, the group-III has participants who have donated blood 4 to 5 times, group-IV has participants who have donated blood more than 5 times, and participants who have never donated blood were in group-V. Happiness and State and Trait Anxiety questionnaire were used to achieve the objectives. A significant difference is found in levels of happiness and state anxiety among the participants of the five groups. Whereas no significant difference is reported in trait anxiety.

Keywords: Emotional states, happiness, anxiety, blood donation, volunteer

Blood donation is a valuable and altruistic act that can save lives and improve the well-being of both the donor and the recipients. Blood donation is a voluntary act that is both important and necessary for maintaining a stable blood supply. Hospitals use donated blood for chronic illnesses, including anaemia, trauma or accident victims, and transfusions during procedures. It's also essential for people with blood abnormalities like haemophilia and cancer patients receiving chemotherapy. Human blood remains a necessary resource that cannot be replaced, even with medical advancements. Donating blood regularly is essential to maintain a sufficient supply and ensure blood is available when needed. Blood donation, while a crucial altruistic act, frequently elicits a range of psychological and physiological responses encompassing both positive emotions such as happiness and contentment, and sometimes negative feelings like anxiety or stress (Martín-Santana & Melián-Alzola, 2022; Hoogerwerf et al., 2017; Gilchrist et al., 2021).

Happiness is a complex and multifaceted concept that has long been the subject of extensive research and scholarly inquiry. Happiness, frequently characterized by feelings of joy, happiness, and satisfaction, can boost a person's quality of life and overall well-being (Lyubomirsky, 2007). The act of giving blood has been shown to elicit positive emotions, such as a sense of fulfilment, purpose, and social connectedness, which can contribute to an individual's overall happiness and life satisfaction (Sojka & Sojka, 2003). The intrinsic benefits that donors receive indicate that prosocial behavior like donating blood can, in fact, promote happy feelings and enhance

well-being (Aknin & Whillans, 2020). Borgonovi (2008) and Meier and Stutzer (2008) found that happiness was higher among volunteers than non-volunteers and there was evidence of positive effects of volunteering on satisfaction with life. Studies have shown a significant relationship between the act of blood donation and an individual's emotions, sense of well-being and overall happiness (Esefeld, Sumnig, Alpen, Grabe, & Greinacher, 2022; Williams, Masser, van Dongen, Thijsen, & Davison, 2018). Many individuals are hesitant to donate for various reasons, such as fear, pain, negative effects of donation, and the sight of blood (Asamoah-Akuoko, Hassal, Bates, & Ullum, 2017). It is also found that these effects vary with BMI, smoking status, age, and sex (Dongen, Williams, Masser, Briggs, Thijsen, & Davison, 2021). Studies have also shown that anxiety significantly influences donor retention, with higher pre-donation anxiety levels negatively associated with the likelihood of repeat donations. The prevalence and intensity of this anxiety can vary depending on individual donor characteristics, prior donation experiences, and specific triggers within the donation procedure itself (France et al., 2013). Moreover, the stress experienced by donors, often predominantly anxiety, has been assessed at various stages of the blood donation process, revealing elevated levels particularly before and during venipuncture (Hoogerwerf et al., 2017). Also, Clowes and Masser (2012) found that "respondents in the affectively hot condition reported significantly higher levels of anxiety about blood donation, as well as less positive attitudes, weaker subjective norms, lower self-efficacy, and lower intention to donate, compared to those in the cool control condition."

This phenomenon presents a significant challenge to donor recruitment and retention efforts worldwide, as fear and anxiety surrounding the donation process can deter potential donors and reduce the return rates of experienced donors (Balaskas et al., 2024; Bani et al., 2024). Understanding these post-donation emotional states is crucial for optimizing donor retention strategies and ensuring a stable blood supply (Dongen, 2015).

Rationale of the Study

Blood donation has been considered to be an act of benevolence for

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years because it is related to saving the lives of people during medical treatments and emergencies. Blood has no substitute and its only source is the human body, so blood donation is very necessary to maintain an adequate supply at different health care facilities. In many places, there is a frequent blood shortage, particularly during emergencies, natural disasters, or pandemics. Improving donor retention is also a big challenge. Research has focused on these aspects and tried to find out the factors that affect the donation behavior; experience is one of them. Experience after the donation can significantly influence whether they donate blood again. Studies have found a positive impact of blood donation, but there is a lack of studies that focus on the number of donations, which examines how the number of blood donations can impact a person's happiness and anxiety, and also the donors and non-donors groups. Also, most of the research focused on the social and environmental factors that determine the donor's experience. The purpose of the present study is to investigate the level of happiness and anxiety of blood donors. The current research can elucidate the impact of blood donation, informing medical professionals and community organizers in promoting awareness, increasing donor participation and ultimately saving lives.

Problem

To assess and compare the happiness and anxiety of the blood donors and non-blood donors.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess and compare the level of happiness of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors.
- To assess and compare the level of anxiety (state & trait) of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There would be a significant difference in the level of happiness of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors.
- There would be a significant difference in the level of state anxiety of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors.
- There would be a significant difference in the level of trait anxiety of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors.

Method

Participants

A purposive sample of 250 male participants from Rohtak district was selected in the present study. 50 participants in each group, i.e., 50 in group-I, 50 in group-II, 50 in group-III, 50 in group-IV, and 50 in group-V. Participants in the donor groups are the regular voluntary blood donors who donate blood at least once a year. The participants of group V have never donated blood. The age range was between 20 to 45 years.

Research Design

A Multi-group design is used in this present study. A five-group design was applied to assess and compare the level of happiness and anxiety of blood donors and non-blood donors. Blood donors comprised four groups, i.e., Group-I (one-time donors), Group-II (two-three times donors), Group-III (four-five times donors), and Group-IV (more than five times donors). The Group-V was comprised non-blood donors.

Blood Donor Groups				
Group-I	Group-II	Group-III	Group-IV	Group-V
One-time Donors Group	Two-Three times Donors Group	Four-Five times Donors Group	More than Five times Donors Group	Non-Blood Donors Group
n=50	n= 50	n= 50	n= 50	n= 50

Measures

Oxford Happiness Questionnaire: The "Oxford Happiness Questionnaire" was developed by Peter Hills and Michael Argyle in year 2002, "to assess the level of Happiness of a person." It covers a wide range of happiness-related experiences, from routine joys to a feeling of fulfilment and purpose. It has 29 items on six-point Likert scale "(from 1 = *strongly disagree*, to 6 = *strongly agree*)." This Questionnaire consist of 29 items, out of which 12 items are scored reversely. The total happiness score is obtained by summing all 29 items and dividing the total by 29. A higher score indicates a higher level of happiness. The scale displays high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha from 0.87 to 0.92) and strong construct validity.

State-Trait Anxiety Inventory: This Inventory (STAI) was developed by Spielberger in association with Gorsuch, Lushene, Vagg, and Jacobs in 1983. It consists of 40 items on a 4-point Likert scale. It measures both "state anxiety (form Y-1) and trait anxiety (form Y-

2)." The state anxiety scale measures "how respondents feel right now at this moment," and the trait anxiety scale assesses "how people generally feel". Higher scores are positively correlated with higher levels of anxiety. Alpha coefficients have ranged from 0.86 to 0.95 for state anxiety and 0.89 to 0.91 for trait anxiety in different groups (Spielberger, 1983). The construct and concurrent validity of the scale are supported by an extensive pool of evidences (Spielberger, 1989).

Procedure

Blood donors who were donating blood voluntarily were approached during the blood donation camps held in Rohtak, Haryana. Eligible blood donors were asked about their donation history and after that, details regarding the study were given to the volunteer blood donors and they were asked to participate in this study. After getting consent from them, the questionnaires with clear instructions were given to the participants. All the participants filled

out the questionnaire. After the completion of questionnaires, they were collected and scoring was done as per norms. After this, SPSS software was used for the statistical analysis.

Results and Discussion

The first objective of the present study was “To assess and compare the level of happiness of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors.” The descriptive statistics were calculated for happiness, which has been presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Happiness of Group-I (One-time Donors), Group-II (Two- three times Donors), Group-III (Four-five Times Donors), Group-IV (more than Five Times Donors) and Group-V (Non-blood Donors)

Groups	N	Mean	SD
Group-I	50	4.30	0.72
Group-II	50	4.35	0.59
Group-III	50	4.45	0.55
Group-IV	50	4.66	0.68
Group-V	50	4.27	0.66

It is observed from the Table 1 that donors who had donated blood more than five times (Group-IV) had a higher mean value on happiness, followed by those who had donated four to five times (Group-III), two to three times (Group-II), and for the first time (Group-I), while non-donors had obtained the lowest mean value on happiness (Group-V).

Table 2

Summary of One-way ANOVA of Happiness

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Between Groups	4.99	4	1.25	3.02*
Within Groups	101.18	245	.41	
Total	106.16	249		

Note. * Significant at 0.05 level

It has been observed that the summary of one-way ANOVA of happiness shows the mean scores on happiness of the participants of five groups (i.e., one-time donors (G-I), two-three times donors (G-II), four-five times donors (G-III), and more than five times donors (G-IV) and non-blood donors (G-V) differed significantly from each other. The F- ratio being 3.02 was found to be significant at 0.05 level. It indicates that all groups are experiencing happiness at different levels. In order to verify which of the five groups actually differed from each other, Tukey's HSD post-hoc test was applied and is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Tukey's HSD Post-hoc Comparison for Happiness between Groups

Groups	Mean Difference
Group-I - Group-II	-0.05
Group-I - Group-III	-0.15
Group-I - Group-IV	-0.36*
Group-I - Group-V	0.03
Group-II - Group-III	-0.10
Group-II - Group-IV	-0.31
Group-II - Group-V	0.08

Group-III - Group-IV	-0.21
Group-III- Group-V	0.18
Group-IV- Group-V	0.39*

Note. * Significant at 0.05 level

From the post-hoc comparison (Table 3), it can be observed that Group IV (more than five times donors) differ significantly from Group-I (one-time donor) and Group V (non-blood donors). The participants of group IV i.e., more than five times donors, experience a significantly higher level of happiness as compared to participants of Group I, i.e., one-time donors and Group-V, i.e., non-blood donors. It indicates that the one-time donors group experiences a significantly lower level of happiness as compared to the more than five times donors' group, with a mean difference of 0.36. Additionally, the group-V experienced a significantly lower level of happiness than group IV with a mean difference of 0.39. However, no significant difference is found in happiness between other groups. The findings suggest that individuals who donate blood more than five times report greater levels of happiness than those who donate only once or have never donated. Repeated blood donation may enhance feelings of personal fulfillment, purpose, and social contribution, which positively influence emotional well-being. Regular donors may also feel a stronger connection to their community, knowing they are consistently contributing to saving lives. Additionally, repeated participation can create a sense of achievement and identity as a committed donor, enhancing the satisfaction level. In contrast, individuals who donated only once or never donated may not experience these psychological and social benefits. The current results are in accordance with the earlier research. Antoni and Marzetti (2022) found that there were significant differences in happiness and subjective well-being between donors and non-donors. Hinrichs et al. (2008) reported that donors exhibit a higher level of well-being than non-donors. Therefore, the present result verifies the first hypothesis.

The second objective of the study was “To assess and compare the level of anxiety (state & trait) of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, and more than five times donors) and non-blood donors.”

The descriptive statistics were calculated for state and trait anxiety, which are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Descriptive Statistics for State and Trait Anxiety of Group-I (One-time Donors), Group-II (Two- three Times Donors), Group-III (Four-five Times Donors), Group-IV (more than Five Times Donors) and Group-V (Non-blood Donors)

Groups	N	Mean		SD	
		State Anxiety	Trait Anxiety	State Anxiety	Trait Anxiety
Group-I	50	37.70	38.04	9.30	8.54
Group-II	50	34.82	38.18	8.00	8.80
Group-III	50	33.88	37.36	8.70	9.28
Group-IV	50	32.38	37.34	8.18	8.52
Group-V	50	32.96	37.02	8.02	9.32

Table 4 exhibits the descriptive statistics for state and trait anxiety. It is evident from the above table that on state anxiety, group-IV has the lowest mean score (32.38), followed by group-V (32.96), group-III (33.88), group-II (34.82) and group-I (37.70). The comparison of

means reflects that Group-IV has the lowest mean value, and Group-I has a high mean value on state anxiety among the donor groups. Further, on trait anxiety, the mean values reflect that Group-V has the lowest mean value (37.02) and Group-II has the highest mean value (38.18) among the donor groups. The description provided above clearly explains the differences in the mean scores on state and trait anxiety, but these differences do not specify the significance of the mean difference. To verify this, one-way ANOVA was applied for further analysis.

Table 5

Summary of One-way ANOVA of State Anxiety

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Between Groups	873.86	4	218.47	3.05*
Within Groups	17522.86	245	71.52	
Total	18396.72	245		

Note. * Significant at 0.05 level

The one-way ANOVA table (Table 5) demonstrates that there is a significant difference among the five groups on state anxiety, $F=3.05$, $p < 0.05$. It indicates that participants of five groups (i.e., "Group-I, Group-II and Group-III, Group-IV and Group-V (non-blood donor group)") differed significantly from each other on state anxiety, which means that participants of all five groups are experiencing different levels of state anxiety. Tukey's HSD was used to determine which pairs of the group means differed significantly.

Table 6

Tukey's HSD Post-hoc Comparison for State Anxiety between Groups

Groups	Mean Difference
Group-I - Group-II	2.88
Group-I - Group-III	3.82
Group-I - Group-IV	5.32*
Group-I - Group-V	4.74*
Group-II - Group-III	0.94
Group-II - Group-IV	2.44
Group-II - Group-V	1.86
Group-III - Group-IV	1.50
Group-III - Group-V	0.92
Group-IV - Group-V	-0.58

Note. * Significant at 0.05 level

From the post-hoc comparison (Table 6), the results indicate that persons who donated blood one-time (group-I) differ significantly from non-blood donors (group-V) and persons who donated blood more than five times (group-IV). However, no significant difference is observed among other groups. It can be concluded that among the five groups, group-I has the highest state anxiety and group-IV has the lowest state anxiety. It implies that one-time donors may experience higher levels of stress due to fear of needles, uncertainty about the procedure and lack of prior experience, which can increase situational anxiety. Non-blood donors may also report relatively high anxiety due to anticipatory fear, misconceptions, and avoidance related to blood donation. In contrast, individuals who have donated more than five times are likely to feel more relaxed and confident, as repeated exposure reduces fear and builds familiarity with the process. Therefore, differences in experience, confidence, and

situational comfort levels may explain the significant variation in state anxiety among the groups. The result is congruence with earlier studies. Asamoah-Akuoko, Hassal, Bates, and Ullum (2017) reported that first-time donors experience higher levels of anxiety due to anticipatory fears about needles, pain, seeing blood, potential fainting, and uncertainty about what will happen during the procedure. France et al. (2021) also found that new donors experience fear and anxiety, which may discourage them from making further donation attempts. Similarly, Saqlain et al. (2023) observed, "frequent blood donations, higher education level and age more than 30 years were associated with reduced blood donation-associated fears among blood donors." Thus, hypothesis 2(a) stated that "there would be a significant difference in the level of state anxiety of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors" is verified.

Regarding trait anxiety, the F-value was calculated and is presented in Table 7.

Table 7

Summary of One-way ANOVA of Trait Anxiety

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Between Groups	49.54	4	12.39	0.16
Within Groups	19409.02	245	79.22	
Total	19458.56	245		

Note. * Significant at 0.05 level

The one-way ANOVA (Table 7) reveals that there is no significant difference among all five groups on trait anxiety, $F=0.16$, $p > 0.05$. It means that subjects of five groups, i.e., G-I (one-time donors), G-II (two-three times donors), G-III (four-five times donors), G-IV (more than five times donors), and G-V (non-blood donors) do not differ on trait anxiety. No significant difference in trait anxiety among the five groups may be observed because trait anxiety reflects a relatively stable personality characteristic rather than a temporary emotional state. Individuals across all groups, whether one-time donors, repeated donors, or non-donors, may share similar baseline personality traits that determine their general anxiety levels. Additionally, blood donation is a voluntary and controlled activity, which may not be strong enough to produce lasting changes in trait anxiety. However, this implies that neither the blood donor group nor the non-blood donor group exhibits any significant differences in trait anxiety. Thus, the 2(b) hypothesis stated that "there would be a significant difference in the level of trait anxiety of blood donors (one-time donors, two-three times donors, four-five times donors, & more than five times donors) and non-blood donors" is not verified from the present findings.

To sum up, it has been observed that a significant difference was found among the five groups in happiness and state anxiety, whereas no significant difference was found in trait anxiety. The study implicates that fears associated with blood donation need to be addressed in reducing anxiety. Further, interventions meant to reduce pre-donation anxiety should concentrate especially on first-time and potential donors by offering reassurance, clear information, and useful coping mechanisms. These initiatives can enhance donors' immediate psychological experience and promote their sustained participation by addressing common obstacles through effective communication, education, and supportive services. Blood

centers should also prioritize anxiety-reduction strategies for first-time donors to increase donor retention, while recruitment campaigns can emphasize long-term psychological rewards (e.g., increased happiness & reduced stress) to motivate continued donation.

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